

solution technique had a significant correlation among the three experiments, showing high consistency and reproducibility of the technique.

Similarity with the results with pot culture and close association with field results (where absolute yields were the indices of salt tolerance) show the

practical validity of this technique.

The technique is simple, quick, and reliable for screening a large number of genotypes. □

Relationship of rice embryo weight and salinity tolerance at seedling stage

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We screened 19 indica and 6 japonica cultivars with varying embryo weights for salt tolerance, using water culture in the IRRI phytotron glasshouse (29/21 °C (day/ night) temperature, 70% relative humidity, natural daylight). Salinity stress of 6800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution. Seedling survival after 2 wk salinization was taken as the criterion for salt tolerance.

Embryo weight/50 seeds ranged from 0.0140 g (Intan Gawri and Palman 46)

Correlation ($r = 0.2151^{ns}$) between embryo weight and seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m). IRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Embryo weight (g)	Survival (%)
Rikuto Norin 15	0.0467	7
Bombilla	0.0454	36
Chang You Zae Rae	0.0450	10
Thatnosubnet	0.0440	12
Jinbu 4	0.0393	45
Pokkali	0.0386	85
Nona Bokra	0.0358	89
IR51491-AC4-6	0.0309	90
IR31779-19-3-3-2-2	0.0302	10
RNR1429	0.0299	18
IR51491-AC4-7	0.0297	82
IR51500-AC9-8	0.0272	32
TNAU (AD) 103	0.0263	8
MI-48	0.0245	2
Khao youth	0.0237	22
IR25924-92-1-3	0.0236	5
Laxmi	0.0227	8
IR28	0.0226	20
Suweon 341	0.0219	70
IR36	0.0209	42
NIAB6	0.0208	25
Duansan	0.0202	18
Basmati 370	0.0195	20
Intan Gawri	0.0140	8
Palman 46	0.0140	2

to 0.0467 g (Rikuto Norin 15). Seedling survival under salinity stress ranged from 2 (Palman 46) to 90 (IR51491-AC4-6).

Among the cultivars studied, the

association between embryo weight and salt tolerance was not significant ($r = 0.2151$) (see table). This finding does not support earlier reports of such an association. □

Ion transport in two rice varieties grown under saline conditions

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Resistance to salt entry into the shoot is often related to survival and growth of plant species. We studied the transport of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ from root to shoot in two rice varieties with different salt tolerances.

NIAB6 (salt tolerant) and IR1561 (salt sensitive) were transplanted at 14 d after seeding into Yoshida nutrient solution. Two salinity levels (0 and 100 mol NaCl) were used. Samples were taken at 7, 14, and 28 d after salinization. Cell sap of whole shoot and root was analyzed and rate of ion transport calculated as

$$J = (M_2 - M_1) / (\overline{WR} \times \Delta T)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are amounts of ion in samples 1 and 2, respectively; \overline{WR} is the log mean root fresh weight (g); and T is difference between harvests, in days.

Rate of Na⁺ transport from root to shoot increased with salinity during both growth periods, but was higher 14 d after salinization (see table).

IR1561 had four times higher Na⁺ transport rate (J_{Na^+}) than NIAB6.

J_{K^+} decreased considerably from 14 to 28 d under no salinity and under 100 mol salinity. At 100 mol salinity, the drop in K⁺ transport (J_{K^+}) in salt-sensitive IR1561 was spectacular.

Rate of ion transport from root to shoot in 2 rice varieties under 2 salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl). Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety	7-14 d		14-28 d	
	0 (control)	100	0 (control)	100
<i>Rate of Na⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	6.0	26.1	2.2	23.7
IR1561	9.2	106.1	1.7	17.9
<i>Rate of K⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	235.4	98.7	80.2	45.3
IR1561	325.4	193.2	78.1	5.9
<i>Rate of Cl⁻ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	30.1	76.6	15.3	26.8
IR1561	37.1	170.2	16.4	33.9

IR1561 had higher J_{K^+} during early stress, but could not maintain the rate of K⁺ transport.

J_{Cl^-} was also much lower for NIAB6 than for IR1561, particularly during the first growth period. It decreased substantially during the second growth period, although it was still higher for IR1561 than for NIAB6. Lower J_{Cl^-} for NIAB6 at high salinity at 14 and 28 d after treatment indicates it has a better Cl⁻ exclusion mechanism.

Zinc:phosphorus ratio — a criterion for salt tolerance in rice

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Different physiological parameters (potassium selectivity [K:Na ratio], exclusion/ inclusion of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in

Effect of salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl) (3 wk stress) on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root of 4 rice varieties and lines.^aFaisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety or line	Fresh wt (g/plant)		Zn ²⁺ (mg/kg dry wt)		P (%)		Zn ²⁺ :P		
	0	100	0	100	0	100	0	100	
	Shoot								
Basmati 370	19.25 a	3.99 c (21)	32.7 d	43.3 b-d	0.224 e	0.281 b	1.46 × 10 ⁻²	1.54 × 10 ⁻²	
NIAB6	19.91 a	7.81 b (39)	41.0 cd	71.3 a	0.163	0.231 d	2.51 × 10 ⁻²	3.09 × 10 ⁻²	
BG402-4	16.52 a	5.94 bc (36)	37.7 d	50.7 b	0.216	0.267 c	1.75 × 10 ⁻²	1.90 × 10 ⁻²	
IR1561	19.50 a	2.96 d (15)	43.3 b-d	51.3 bc	0.231 d	0.287 a	1.87 × 10 ⁻²	1.79 × 10 ⁻²	
Mean	18.80 A	5.18 B	38.7 B	54.7 A	0.208 B	0.266 A	1.64 × 10 ⁻²	2.68 × 10 ⁻²	
	Root								
Basmati 370	21.12 ab	5.98 d (28)	43.3 b	43.3 b	0.131 d	0.157 b	3.30 × 10 ⁻²	2.76 × 10 ⁻²	
NIAB6	19.69 ab	9.46 c (48)	58.7 a	62.3 a	0.127 d	0.157 b	4.62 × 10 ⁻²	3.97 × 10 ⁻²	
BG402-4	18.82 b	10.13 c (54)	56.0 a	56.7 a	0.131 c	0.152 a	4.27 × 10 ⁻²	3.73 × 10 ⁻²	
IR1561	23.12 a	4.10 d (18)	59.7 a	55.0 a	0.141 c	0.195 a	4.23 × 10 ⁻²	2.82 × 10 ⁻²	
Mean	20.55 A	7.42 B	54.4 A	53.3 A	0.132 B	0.165 A	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.32 × 10 ⁻²	

^aMeans with different letters differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05). The Zn²⁺: P ratio is calculated when the concentration of Zn and P is in percent. Values in the parentheses represent percentages of respective controls.

various plant tissues, ionic balance, osmotic adjustment, etc.) are related to a plant's salt tolerance. Many workers have used these physiological traits to screen rice genotypes for salt tolerance. We determined the effect of external salinity on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root. Seedlings of four rice varieties were transferred at 14 d to foam-plugged holes (1 cm diam) in thermoplastic sheets floating on Yoshida nutrient solution at two salinity levels: 0

and 100 mol NaCl in plastic tubs. Plants were harvested after 3 wk, separated into shoot and root, dried, and Zn and P contents determined.

Zn²⁺ concentration in the shoot increased significantly with external salinity of 100 mol NaCl; in the root, it was not affected by salt stress (see table). Zn concentration in the shoot of salt-tolerant NIAB6 was significantly higher than in the other varieties. Zn concentration in roots of NIAB6 was

significantly higher than that of Basmati 370 (which had the lowest Zn²⁺ concentration in shoot and root).

Salt-sensitive IR1561 had significantly higher P concentration in shoot and root than all other varieties; salt-tolerant NIAB6 had significantly lower shoot P concentration than all other varieties.

Zn:P ratios in shoot and root were highest in NIAB6 and lowest in Basmati 370 with and without salt stress. These ratios were also low in IR1561. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Two modern photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties for Bangladesh

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BRRI recently released modern photoperiod-sensitive varieties BR22 and BR23 for T. aman season in Bangladesh.

BR22 was developed from Nizersail/BR51-46-5; BR23 was derived from DA29/ BR4. Both varieties are suitable for late planting in T. aman. Yield potential and disease reactions are comparable to those of existing modern

Grain yield and plant height of 2 new varieties for Bangladesh.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
		1st planting	2d planting
BR22	115	4.4	3.4
BR23	120	4.6	3.7
BR11 (check)	110	3.8	1.3
Nizersail (local check)	132	3.1	2.6

^aAverage of 3 yr at 4 regional stations. 1st planting: 4-15 Aug with 30-d-old seedlings, 2d planting: 15-22 Sep with 40-d-old seedlings.

varieties, but the new varieties yield more than 1 t higher in late plantings (see table).

BR22 has medium bold grain with intermediate amylose content and

moderate resistance to tungro (RTV), bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, sheath blight (ShB), and blast.

BR23 has long slender grain with intermediate amylose content and moderate resistance to RTV, stem rot, ShB, and submergence tolerance. □

RAU4045-2A — a very short duration cultivar for harsh upland environments

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RAU4045-2A (IET9790), a semidwarf variety derived from Fine Gora/ IET2832, has resistance to brown spot and grain discoloration and